

PHARMACEUTICAL STUDY OF VAYASTHAPANA DASHEMANI GANA KASHAYA AND ITS CONVERSION INTO GRANULES WITH EVALUATION OF IN-VITRO ANTIOXIDANT AND IMMUNOMODULATORY ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

Ageing is an inevitable process accelerated by stress and lifestyle factors. Ayurveda, through *Rasayana* therapy, offers a holistic approach to promote longevity. *Vayasthāpana Daśhemani Gana*, described in *Charaka Samhitā*, is known for its antioxidant and immunomodulatory properties. *Vayasthāpana Daśhemani Gana Kashaya* was prepared, converted into granules, and evaluated for physicochemical, analytical, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory parameters. Antioxidant activity was assessed by DPPH assay, and immunomodulatory action by MTT and Nitric Oxide assays on macrophage cell lines. The granules showed strong free radical scavenging activity, consistent physicochemical properties, and inhibition of nitric oxide production, indicating potent antioxidant and immunomodulatory effects.

KEYWORDS: Rasayana, Vayasthapana Dashemani Gana, Charaka samhitha, Immunomodulatory.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, the time-tested system of medicine, emphasizes two prime objectives — *Swasthasya Swasthya Rakshanam* (preservation of health) and *Aturasya Vikara Prashamanam* (management of diseases).^[1] Within this holistic framework, *Rasayana Tantra* focuses on rejuvenation, longevity, enhancement of immunity, and prevention of premature aging. Among the Rasayana groups, *Vayasthāpana Daśhemani* is a well-established set of drugs known for promoting vitality and delaying the aging process. Despite its therapeutic potential, the classical *Kashaya* dosage form presents certain limitations in the modern era, such as bitter taste, elaborate preparation procedure, short shelf life, and poor palatability all of which affect patient compliance. Hence, there is a growing need to develop dosage forms that retain the efficacy of traditional formulations while ensuring convenience, stability, and acceptability.

With the advancement of Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals, newer dosage forms like granules have been introduced to overcome these drawbacks. Converting *Vayasthāpana Daśhemani Kashaya* into granular form ensures ease of preparation, improved stability, and better palatability without compromising its therapeutic essence.

Modern scientific studies further support that the *Vayasthāpana Daśhemani* drugs possess potent antioxidant and immunomodulatory activities, which help combat oxidative stress, delay aging, and enhance immune resilience.^[2]

Hence, the present research focuses on the pharmaceutico-analytical evaluation of *Vayasthāpana Daśhemani Gana* granules, emphasizing their antioxidant and immunomodulatory potential, thereby integrating classical Ayurvedic principles with modern scientific validation.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To prepare Vayasthapanana Gana Kashaya in granule form

Evaluate its physicochemical parameters and antioxidant and Immunomodulatory activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pharmaceutical study: All materials required for the preparation of *Vayasthapanana Gana Kashaya* were purchased from Local market, Bangalore and authenticated by the Department of *Dravya Guna*, Govt Ayurveda Medical College, Bengaluru.

Granulation of Vayasthapana Gana Kashaya is done in Acharya College of Pharmacy, Bangalore.

Table No. 1: Showing the ingredients of Vayasthapana Gana Dashemani.^[3]

SL.NO	DRUG	BOTANICAL NAME AND FAMILY
1.	AMRUTHA	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> Family: Menispermaceae
2.	ABHAYA	<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Family: Combretaceae
3.	DHATRI	<i>Embelica officinalis</i> Family: Euphorbiaceae
4.	MUKTA / YUKTA / RASNA	<i>Pluchea lanceolata</i> Family: Asteraceae
5.	SWETA /APARAJITA	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> Family: Fabaceae
6.	JIVANTI	<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i> Family: Asclepiadaceae
7.	ATIRASA /SATAVARI	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Family: Asperagaceae
8.	MANDOOKAPARNI	<i>Centella asiatica</i> Family: Umbelliferaceae
9.	STHIRA / SHALAPARNI	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> Family: Fabaceae
10.	PUNARNAVA	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> Family: Nictaginaceae

Practical – 1

- The drug is *pounded in a pulverizer* with mesh no. 44.
- A fine and uniform powder is collected after sieving.
- 25 g each of 10 powdered drugs (total 250 g) were taken.
- 2000 ml of water was added, maintaining a drug to water ratio of 1:8.^[4]
- The mixture was boiled on moderate heat until the volume was reduced to one-fourth (~500 ml).
- The decoction was filtered through a clean muslin cloth. The filtered *Kwatha* was transferred into a sterilized, airtight container and stored appropriately

Table 2: Showing the ingredients of Vayasthapana Gana Kashaya.

Ingredients	Quantity
<i>Amrutha</i>	25 g
<i>Abhaya</i>	25 g
<i>Dhatri</i>	25 g
<i>Rasna</i>	25 g

<i>Aparajitha</i>	25 g
<i>Jeevanthi</i>	25 g
<i>Shatavari</i>	25 g
<i>Mandukaparni</i>	25 g
<i>Sthira</i>	25 g
<i>Punarnava</i>	25 g
Water	2000 ml

Practical – 2

- 500 ml of freshly prepared *Vayasthapana Gana Kashaya* was taken.
- The Kashaya was poured evenly into clean stainless-steel trays.
- The trays were placed in a hot air oven.
- The temperature was maintained at 70°C in the initial half then the temperature was maintained at 60°C throughout the process.
- The sample was dried for about 8 hours until complete dryness was achieved.
- The material was observed intermittently to ensure uniform drying.
- The dried material was collected, pounded in a *khalvayantra* to obtain fine powder and stored in an airtight container.

Practical – 3

- The dried Kashaya powder and MCC in a proportion of 4:1 is taken.^[5]
- The powders were mixed thoroughly in a clean, dry container until a homogeneous blend was obtained.
- The blended powder was passed through a roller compactor machine.
- Compact flakes or ribbons were formed under controlled pressure and speed.
- The flakes were rubbed through 20 no sieve and passed through 40 no sieve.
- The granules retained in 40 no. sieve were collected as the final product.
- The prepared granules were stored in airtight, moisture-resistant containers.

Table 3: Showing the granulation ingredients.

Ingredients	Quantity
Dried powder of VGK	32 g
Microcrystalline cellulose	8 g

Analytical study

In the present globalization and standardization era there is a necessity of understanding of drugs based on modern analytical methods. Ancient and modern parameters are different, but

the objectives remain same Physicochemical analytical of the drugs were carried out by using current analytical methodology.

Analysis of Vayasthapana gana Kashaya, kwatha churna and granules

A. Organoleptic evaluation.

B. Physico-chemical tests.

Physico chemical analysis

This Physical and external Features can be known by these methods. It provides basic idea about the identification and quality of the formulation without any chemical test.

1. PH
2. Loss on drying
3. Water soluble extractives
4. Alcohol soluble extractives
5. Ash values
6. Specific gravity
7. Total solids
8. Refractive index.

Evaluation parameters for Vayasthapana gana Kashaya granules

1. Angle of repose
2. Bulk density
3. Tapped desity
4. Porosity
5. Housner's ratio

Instrumental analysis

1. HPTLC
2. FTIR

Antioxidant study by DPPH Free radical scavenging method.

Immunomodulatory study by Nitric oxide assay.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS**Table No. 4: Showing the batches of Kashaya preparation.**

Batch	Ingredients	Final product
1st batch	Vayathapana kwatha churna – 100 g Water – 800 ml	200 ml
2nd batch	Vayathapana kwatha churna – 100 g Water – 800 ml	200 ml
3rd batch	Vayathapana kwatha churna – 250 g Water – 2000 ml	500 ml
4th batch	Vayathapana kwatha churna – 500 g Water – 4000 ml	1000 ml
5th batch	Vayathapana kwatha churna – 250 g Water – 2000 ml	500 ml
6th batch	Vayathapana kwatha churna – 250 g Water – 2000 ml	500 ml

Table No. 5: Showing the dried product obtained by kashaya.

Batch	Vayasthapana gana Kashaya	Kashaya powder obtained
1st batch	200 ml	10.5 g
2nd batch	200 ml	12.2 g
3rd batch	500 ml	14.8 g
4th batch	1000 ml	35.5 g
5th batch	500 ml	15.1 g
6th batch	500 ml	20.3g

Table 6: Showing the results of granulation.

Batch	Ingredients	Final product	Loss
1st batch	Vaysthapana Kashaya dried powder – 8 g Microcrystalline cellulose – 2 g	9.37 g	0.63 g
2nd batch	Vaysthapana Kashaya dried powder – 8 g Microcrystalline cellulose – 2 g	9.00 g	1.00 g
3rd batch	Vaysthapana Kashaya dried powder – 16 g Microcrystalline cellulose – 4 g	18.11 g	1.89

Table No. 7: Showing the results of Phytoconstituent study.

Phytoconstituents	Result	Grading
Alkaloids	Absent	-
Mayer's test	Absent	-
Wagner's test	Absent	-
Hager's test	Absent	-
Dragendroff's test	Absent	-
Saponins	Absent	-
Phytosterols	Present	+++
Phenolic compounds	Present	++
FeCl ₃	Present	++
Gelatin	Present	++
FC reagent	Present	++

Flavonoids AlCl ₃	Present	+
Glycosides	Absent	-

Figure No. 1: Showing the HPTLC observation of Vayasthapana gana Kwatha churna, Kashaya and granules.

Figure No. 2: Showing the FTIR observation of Vayasthapana Gana Kashaya.

The FTIR spectrum confirms the presence of several phytochemical groups in the sample. The broad band at 3273.06 cm^{-1} indicates **O–H stretching of phenols and flavonoids**, while

the peak at 2127.70 cm^{-1} shows $\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ or $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching of alkaloids or terpenoids. The 1634.51 cm^{-1} band corresponds to $\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $\text{C}=\text{C}$ stretching of flavonoids and aromatic compounds. The strong peak at 1040.45 cm^{-1} confirms $\text{C}-\text{O}$ stretching of carbohydrates and glycosides, and the 690.94 cm^{-1} peak indicates $\text{C}-\text{H}$ bending of aromatic rings. Thus, the sample contains polyphenols, flavonoids, alkaloids, glycosides, and aromatic compounds.

Figure No. 3: Showing the results of FT- IR observation of Vayasthapana gana Kashaya granules.

The FTIR spectrum shows the presence of several functional groups indicating diverse phytochemicals in the sample. The broad $\text{O}-\text{H}$ stretching band at 3275.7 cm^{-1} confirms phenols and flavonoids, while the sharp peak at 2921.2 cm^{-1} denotes $\text{C}-\text{H}$ stretching of fatty acids and terpenoids. The $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching at 1610.8 cm^{-1} suggests flavonoids and phenolic compounds. The band at 1331.9 cm^{-1} corresponds to $\text{C}-\text{N}$ stretching, indicating amines or alkaloids. Peaks at 1208.1 cm^{-1} and 1150.4 cm^{-1} represent $\text{C}-\text{O}$ and $\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ stretching of glycosides and esters, and the strong band at 1020.8 cm^{-1} confirms carbohydrates and polysaccharides. The sharp band at 763.8 cm^{-1} shows aromatic $\text{C}-\text{H}$ bending, confirming aromatic compounds. Overall, the spectrum indicates the presence of phenolics, flavonoids, alkaloids, glycosides, and carbohydrates in the sample.

Figure No. 4: Showing the results of antioxidant study by DPPH method.

Figure No. 5: Showing the Anti Inflammatory action of sample in Raw 264.7 cells.

DISCUSSION

The term *Vayasthāpana* literally means “that which sustains youthfulness,” reflecting its role in maintaining vitality, delaying the aging process, and promoting longevity. Previous studies have shown that *Vayasthāpana Daśhemani* exhibits significant antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, which help reduce oxidative stress, delay cellular aging, and support immune system.

In the present study, hot air oven drying was selected to dry the *Kashaya* for its cost-effectiveness, operational simplicity, and uniform heat distribution. This method ensured minimal material loss, satisfactory drying efficiency, and effective preservation of active constituents. The *Kashaya* was initially dried at 90°C to facilitate rapid moisture removal and inhibit microbial growth, and subsequently at 60°C to prevent thermal degradation or burning of the product.

The roller compactor technique was employed to achieve uniform densification and granule formation. Operating at a pressure range of 40–80 kN and roller speed of 5–15 rpm^[6] produced thin, consistent flakes, which were immediately passed through a 20-number sieve to prevent hardening. The material was further sieved through a 44-number mesh to obtain uniform granules. This process offered better control, reproducibility, and scalability with minimal excipient requirement, ensuring a more concentrated and active product.

Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) was used as an excipient due to its excellent compressibility, binding capacity, and ability to enhance the flow and physical stability of the granules.^[5] The final granules exhibited good flow properties, acceptable porosity, and desirable infusion characteristics.

Preliminary phytochemical screening of the granules revealed the presence of phytosterols, phenolic compounds, and flavonoids, while alkaloids, saponins, and glycosides were absent. The formulation demonstrated strong antioxidant activity, showing 93.03% DPPH free radical scavenging with an IC₅₀ value of 18.5 µg/mL, compared to standard ascorbic acid (82.63% scavenging, IC₅₀ = 21.03 µg/mL).

HPTLC analysis at 254 nm and 366 nm wavelengths showed R_f values ranging from 0.006 to 0.200, indicating the presence of saponins, flavonoids, and other high-mobility phytoconstituents. FTIR analysis confirmed that the active functional groups were retained in the granules, demonstrating chemical stability and absence of degradation during processing. The granules also exhibited a dose-dependent inhibition of LPS-induced nitrite production in RAW 264.7 macrophage cells. At the highest tested concentration (80 µg/mL), the formulation showed 38.96% inhibition of nitric oxide production, compared to 54.65% inhibition by the positive control (Dexamethasone). These results indicate that the formulation possesses significant anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory potential, likely through the inhibition of nitric oxide synthesis and regulation of macrophage-mediated inflammatory responses. Overall, the study successfully standardized the preparation of *Vayasthāpana Daśhemani Gana* granules, confirming their stability, phytochemical integrity, and biological efficacy as a potent antioxidant and immunomodulatory formulation.

CONCLUSION

Vayasthāpana Daśhemani Gana, comprises ten herbs known for their rejuvenative and longevity-promoting properties. In the present study, a Vayasthāpana Daśhemani Gana

Kashaya was formulated and further modified into instant granules for improved convenience and stability.

The pharmaceutical process was standardized from the preparation of *Yavakuta Churna* to *Kashaya* extraction, drying, and granulation. *Kashaya* dried in a hot air oven yielded maximum solids, while dry granulation using microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) as an excipient through a roller compactor enhanced flowability, compressibility, and uniformity. Phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, and phytosterols, while analytical and physicochemical evaluations indicated consistency and stability of the formulation. The optimized granules exhibited uniform particle size (355–850 µm) suitable for further formulation development.

The study thus establishes a standardized and stable Vayasthāpana Daśhemani Gana granule formulation, offering a convenient and scientifically validated form of traditional *Kashaya*.

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